

**DEGREE COLLEGES OF SINDHUDURG DISTRICT VIEWED FROM THE
LENS OF TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT: IMPLICATION
TO TOTAL QUALITY EDUCATION**

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Abstract-

The quality concept was initially focused on tangible products manufactured by industrial organizations later it covered services like municipal services, police, health & education. In the prevailing environment of globalization & free market the concept of total quality management has become the essential prerequisite for the success of any service dealing with any product rather service. TQM in education has a basic difficulty in measurement. Quality in higher education is reflected in evaluation of students' attainment but it is very difficult to measure the contribution of various factors for the rise in quality. This study focuses on perception of students towards total quality management in higher education institutions in the district of Sindhudurg. This is the objective of the study. For present study the researcher uses descriptive method of survey type. The tool was prepared by the researcher. Twelve Degree Colleges in Sindhudurg District were the population of the study. Out of 12 colleges 8 were aided colleges and 4 were un-aided colleges were randomly selected and students were randomly selected. The sample selected for the study was based on simple random sampling technique. In this study total quality management has been explored by covering three aspects regarding Human resources management, Operating procedure and Organizational Commitment. In order to examine the quality of education and its three aspects mean, standard deviation and t-test were applied. Findings of the study shows there was difference in the perception of students about human resources management, operating procedure and there was no difference in the perception of students' about organizational commitment.

Introduction

Main indicators of quality are relevance & excellence. Relevance shows the difference between caliber while excellence shows the height of the performance. It is very difficult to measure the contribution of various factors for the rise in quality. Quality in teaching is influenced by the response of the student. In fact, quality may vary at different times & in different circumstances. Due to presence of human element an aspect of unpredictability is there depending on the physical & mental status of education. The quality concept was initially focused on tangible product manufactured by industrial organizations later to cover services like municipal services, police, health & education. In the prevailing environment of globalization & free market the concept of total quality management has become the essential prerequisite for the success of any service dealing with any product rather service. TQM in education has a basic difficulty in measurement. One of the approaches to assess quality in higher education is reflected in the evaluation of students' perception of quality. This approach is however difficult as students perceptions are difficult to capture.

In TQM the main focus is on customer satisfaction. Mahatma Gandhi has the following to say about a customer –

1. A customer (student) is the most important visitor on our premises.
2. He is not dependent on us, we are dependent on him.
3. He is not an interruption on our work, he is purpose of it.
4. He is not an outsider to our business; he is a part of it.
5. We are not doing him a favour by serving him. He is doing us a favour by giving us an opportunity to do so (Gyani Girdhar 1997)

Thus development of student is the basic purpose of education.

RESEARCH PROBLEM-:

Degree Colleges of Sindhudurg district viewed from the lens of Total Quality Management: Implication to Total Quality Education.

AIM:-

1. To study students' perceptions of total quality management in higher education institutions

OBJECTIVES

- To study perceptions of students about Human Resource Management on the basis of following type of institutions
 - A)Aided Colleges
 - B)Un-Aided Colleges
- To study perceptions of students about Operating Procedure of colleges on the basis of following types of institutions
 - A)Aided Colleges
 - B)Un-Aided Colleges
- To study perceptions of students about Organizational Commitment on the basis of following type of Institution
 - A)Aided Colleges
 - B)Un-Aided Colleges

HYPOTHESIS

- 1) **Ho:** There is no significant difference between perceptions of students about Human Resource Management on the basis of following type of institutions
 - A)Aided Colleges
 - B) Un-Aided Colleges
- 2) **Ho:** There is no significant difference between perceptions of students about Operating Procedure on the basis of following type of institutions
 - A) Aided Colleges
 - B) Un-Aided Colleges
- 3) **Ho:** There is no significant difference between perceptions of Students about Organizational Commitment on the basis of following type of institutions
 - A)Aided Colleges
 - B)Un-Aided Colleges

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Total Quality Management:-

is an ongoing process which educational managers' use, to enable everyone in the college to continuously improve their abilities so as to meet and exceed internal and external customer expectations. It is also referred to as continuous quality improvement of college. Total Quality Management has been operationalised in terms of

Human Resource Management (HRM)

is the function within an organization that focuses on recruitment of, management of, and providing direction for the people who work in the organization. HRM is the organizational function that deals with issues related to people such as compensation, hiring, performance management, organization development, safety, wellness, benefits, employee motivation, communication, administration, and training.

Operating Procedure-

a procedure for operating something or for dealing with a given situation.

Organizations Commitment-

Strength of the feeling of responsibility that an employee has towards the mission of the organization.

Perception - the ability to see or hear or become aware of something

District:- is defined as a geographical area delimited by certain boundaries.

Sindhudurg:- is a geographical area consisted of six talukas viz. Sawantwadi, Kudal

NEED –

Review tells that few study this type has been done earlier. The need of the study the perception of students and parents towards Total Quality Management felt due to following reasons.

- 1) Low Enrolment at Higher Education.

- 2) High Dropouts at School Education
- 3) Poor Quality of Education both at School as well as Higher Education level.
- 4) Low employability

SIGNIFICANCE -:

The present study focuses on Total Quality Management in education. Hence this study will benefit all educational institution who wishes to provide quality education to their students. The research will benefit the parent's community. Furthermore the parents can also plan as to how they can contribute towards improving the standards of college. It may bring awareness among students related to quality management

SCOPE-:

Scope refers to area of study. The study investigates perception of Students towards total quality management of Degree Colleges of Sindhudurg District

LIMITATIONS-:

The study is restricted to Marathi Medium College. The response to the tools was restricted to students was studying in Degree Colleges in the District of Sindhudurg.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

For the present research researcher use of **descriptive method of survey** type

SAMPLE-

The sample selected for the study was based on Simple Random Sample technique. The sample in the present research comprises 22 students of twelve Degree Colleges from the district of Sindhudurg.

Tools Used-

For the present study tool was prepared last year by Kishori Anant Mestry. The content validity of the perception scale was established. . Researcher had given the tool to 5 experts and educationists for validation. For determining the reliability of the tool, the researcher has used Cronbach alpha method and the reliability value of the tool is 0.81 which is higher than .50 and for the stability of items , internal consistency test was used .

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The contribution of the statistical techniques is considerably high in the process of analyzing the data. In the present study, two types of analyses are adopted:

1. Descriptive Analysis
2. Inferential Analysis

The 't' test is used to see difference between Perception of students of aided colleges and un aided Degree colleges .

FINDINGS

The main conclusions that emerged out of the study were:

HYPOTHESIS

Ho: There is no significant difference between Perceptions of students about Human

Resource Management, Operating Procedure and Organizational Commitment **on** the basis

of following type of institutions

- a) Aided Colleges
- b) Un-Aided Colleges

Table-2 Perception of the students about Human Resource Management, Operating Procedure and Organizational Commitment **on** the basis type of Institution

Sr. No	Dimensions	Group	N	Mean	SD	t value	p	
1	Human Resource Management	Aided Colleges	176	45.80	5.33	2.45	0.05	Significant
		Un-Aided Colleges	90	44.28	4.55		0.05	
2	Operating Procedure	Aided Colleges	176	52.42	6.70	2.87	0.05	Significant
		Un-Aided Colleges	90	50.12	6.01		0.05	

3	Organizational Commitment	Aided Colleges	176	51.63	6.09	0.50	0.05	N.S.
		Un-Aided Colleges	90	52.32	4.90		0.05	

df=264

The null hypothesis states that there is no significance difference in perception of students about Human Resource Management in Aided Colleges and Non-Aided Colleges of Sindhudurg District. The statistical technique used to test this hypothesis was t-test. The obtained value of 't' is 2.45, which is higher than that the tabulated 't' value at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the study reveals that there is significant difference in Degree colleges students perception of Total Quality Management in Aided and Un-Aided Colleges. The Mean value of aided colleges students are greater than un-aided colleges students. Hence aided colleges students have a higher perception than un-aided colleges.

This indicates that in aided colleges have better human resource management procedures in place. That is students perceive aided colleges deals with issues related to people such as compensation, hiring, performance management, organization development, safety, wellness as compared to unaided colleges.

The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in perception of students about Operating Procedure in Aided Colleges and Non-Aided Colleges of Sindhudurg District. The statistical technique used to test this hypothesis was t-test. The obtained value of 't' is 2.87, which is higher than that the tabulated 't' value at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the study reveals that there is significant difference in Degree colleges students perception of Total Quality Management in Aided and Un-Aided Colleges. The Mean value of aided colleges students are greater than un-aided colleges students. Hence aided colleges students have a higher perception than un-aided colleges

This indicates that in aided colleges after the admission process in orientation programme students come to know about curriculum and practical also and overall operating procedure of the Institute. In unaided colleges process of admission takes a lot of time and at the time of orientation programme all the students may not be able to present and students do not get any detail information about operating procedure of the Institute about time table, fees distribution, rules and regulations of the Institute.

The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in perception of students about Organization Commitment in Aided Colleges and Non-Aided Colleges of Sindhudurg District. The statistical technique used to test this hypothesis was t-test. The obtained value of 't' is 0.50, which is less than that the tabulated 't' value at 0.05 level of significance.

Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the study reveals that there is no significant difference in Degree colleges' students' perception of Total Quality Management in Aided and Non-Aided Colleges. The students of aided colleges and un-aided colleges always respect and love the Institution a lot.

Conclusion:-

There is significant difference in the perception of students about Human Resource Management, Operating Procedure on the basis of type of the Institutions. There is no significant difference in the perception of students towards Organizational Commitment

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